

1 **Water Vapor Vertical Distribution on Mars after Six**
2 **Years of TGO/NOMAD Solar Occultations. Part II:**
3 **Cross-validation within TGO and comparison with**
4 **models**

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19 **Key Points:**

- 20 • Cross-validation between NOMAD and ACS water vapor observations shows good
21 agreement despite differing methods.
- 22 • Mars PCM reproduces the observed NOMAD climatology but shows discrepancies
23 likely due to the modeled global circulation and water supersaturation.
- 24 • Cluster analysis applied to NOMAD vertical profiles identifies seasonal and latitudinal
25 unique profiles, providing a simplified climatology.

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Abstract

This is the second part of an investigation of water vapor in the Martian atmosphere using solar occultation observations by the spectrometer NOMAD on board the ExoMars Trace Gas Orbiter. Following the analysis performed in the first part, hereafter named as Paper I, a cross-validation exercise between NOMAD and ACS results is presented, showing global as well as profile-by-profile comparisons. The results revealed an overall good agreement between different teams and instruments, taking into account the different retrieval methodologies. In order to compare with model predictions, we performed an exhaustive analysis of the water vapor simulated by Mars Planetary Climate Model (MPCM). It shows that the MPCM reproduces most of the water vapor climatological features observed in the atmosphere. However, several discrepancies between model and observations are noticed. Some of these possibly related to the vertical distribution of dust and its effect on the global circulation and on the water vapor vertical transport. Other data-model differences found at 60 km seem to be related to discrepancies on the water ice cloud formation in the MPCM. In addition, we included a cluster analysis of Martian water vapor vertical profiles for the first time. This technique applied to MPCM and NOMAD water vapor retrievals revealed distinct groups of profiles being representative of specific seasons and latitudinal regions, similarly distributed in both model and observations. Moreover, it allowed us to provide a simplified water vapor climatology, useful to detect out-of-season events and biases in the retrieval processes.

Plain Language Summary

This study is a follow-up to a previous paper focused on the analysis of Martian water vapor vertical profiles. We make profit of the large data set to compare water vapor measurements from two instruments, NOMAD and ACS, both onboard the ExoMars Trace Gas Orbiter (TGO). These comparisons show good agreement between the instruments, despite differences in how the data is processed by different teams. To further validate our findings, this study compares these measurements to simulated water vapor vertical profiles from the Mars Planetary Climate Model (MPCM). The model generally manages to reproduce the observed water vapor seasonal and latitudinal patterns on Mars, although there are some notable discrepancies. These differences between model and observations are linked to how the model handles the distribution of dust and its impact on the global circulation, as well as possible misinterpretations in simulating the formation of water ice clouds at high altitudes. Additionally, our study introduces a new post processing methodology on Mars water vertical profiles: cluster analysis. This approach simplifies the analysis of water vapor patterns and helps identify unusual events or potential issues with the data processing.

1 Introduction

Although water vapor is relatively scarce on Mars, it plays a key role in several surface and atmospheric interactions, including regolith-atmosphere exchange, chemical and photochemical reactions, nucleation, sublimation, and transport. Its distribution is influenced by these processes and temperature variations, making it a fundamental component of the planet's complex climate. Understanding the behavior, sources, and variability of water vapor on Mars, both today and in the past, is vital to reconstructing the planet's climatic and geological evolution, as Mars has transitioned from a warmer, wetter environment to the cold, dry conditions we observe today.

Knowledge about water vapor vertical distribution has been limited until recent years. Mars' thin atmosphere, with surface pressures only about 1% of Earth's, makes detecting and measuring trace gases challenging and most information so far came from nadir-looking orbital observations, which provided integrated column abundances (Smith, 2002), and global circulation models (Forget et al., 1999; Haberle et al., 2019). However,

76 the application of the solar occultation technique, widely used for atmospheric studies
 77 on Earth, has enabled an unprecedented sensitivity for detecting and profiling water vapor
 78 and other trace species at different altitudes in the Martian atmosphere.

79 This study, the second in a two-part series, presents the continuation of the analysis
 80 of water vapor in the Martian atmosphere presented in Part I (Brines, López-Valverde,
 81 Funke, Galindo, et al., 2025), using data from over 7,000 solar occultations by the NOMAD
 82 (Nadir and Occultation for Mars Discovery) instrument onboard the ExoMars Trace Gas
 83 Orbiter (TGO). The high sensitivity of the NOMAD instrument allowed us to obtain
 84 water vapor abundances from $\sim 5 - 10$ km up to $\sim 110 - 120$ km altitude.
 85 The analysis in Part I revealed significant seasonal and latitudinal variations, with the
 86 most striking differences observed between perihelion and aphelion seasons. During perihelion,
 87 the southern hemisphere experiences much higher and more extended water vapor concentrations,
 88 particularly during its summer. These seasonal patterns are influenced by multiple factors,
 89 including Martian orbital eccentricity, dust storms, sublimation from polar ice caps, and
 90 the planet's topography (Barnes et al., 2017). Notably, during Martian years (MY) 35
 91 and 36, they observed enhanced vertical transport of water vapor at 60°S , where abundances
 92 reached about 50 ppm at 100 km altitude during specific solar longitude (L_S) periods
 93 close to the perihelion, confirming previous studies on this same feature (Brines et al.,
 94 2024; Belyaev et al., 2021). Additionally, the Global Dust Storm (GDS) in MY 34 injected
 95 significant amounts of water vapor into the upper atmosphere, with concentrations reaching
 96 100 ppm at 80 km altitude after the northern autumn equinox as previously shown in
 97 Brines et al. (2023). The study presented in Part I, improving previous works on TGO
 98 data and extending the vertical coverage up to 120 km altitude, also revealed that water
 99 vapor profiles are consistently more vertically extended and abundant during the evenings
 100 than the mornings throughout all years, attributing this systematic effect to stronger vertical
 101 transport during daytime. In addition, an unusual enhancement in vertical transport was
 102 observed in MY 37 during the aphelion season in the northern hemisphere, at $L_S = 112^\circ$,
 103 a phenomenon not seen in previous years.

104 Building on the Part I, which outlined the methodology and initial findings, this paper
 105 focuses into the detailed comparison, cross-validation and statistical analysis of water
 106 vapor vertical profiles from different instruments and research teams across MYs 34 to
 107 37. The extensive data set used in this series of papers permitted a robust comparison
 108 between other NOMAD and ACS results revealing overall a good agreement between different
 109 teams and instruments. In addition, a global comparison of water vapor vertical profiles
 110 measured by NOMAD and those simulated by the Mars Planetary Climate Model (MPCM)
 111 showed a systematic overestimation of water vapor abundances in the model under dusty
 112 atmospheric conditions and, for the first time, an application of cluster analysis techniques
 113 to Martian water vapor vertical profiles is presented. The structure of this paper is as
 114 follows: In Section 2 we describe the details about the NOMAD instrument and the analysis
 115 of the absorption spectra. The comparison between NOMAD and ACS is presented in
 116 Section 3. The NOMAD-MPCM comparison is shown in Section 4. The cluster analysis
 117 applied to both NOMAD profiles and MPCM simulated profiles is presented in Section
 118 5. The interpretation and discussion of the results is shown in Section 6. Finally, Section
 119 7 summarizes the results highlighting the main conclusions of this work. A Supporting
 120 Information document is included, showing a detailed profile-by-profile comparison and
 121 additional insights for the NOMAD-GCM comparison and cluster analysis.

122 2 Data set and analysis

123 Since in Part I of this series of papers the data set and retrieval methodology are
 124 thoroughly described, in this Part II we decided to briefly summarize that information.
 125 Hence, for a more detailed description, please refer to Part I (Brines, López-Valverde,
 126 Funke, Galindo, et al., 2025).

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2.1 The NOMAD instrument and data analysis

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The NOMAD instrument is a suit of three spectrometers able to sample the Martian atmosphere in different viewing geometries and at different spectral ranges operating between 0.2 to 4.3 μm covering the UV, visible and infrared (IR) regions of the spectrum (Vandaele et al., 2018). The Solar Occultation (SO) channel dedicated for solar occultation measurements in the IR (2.3-4.3 μm), was designed based upon the Solar Occultation in the Infrared (SOIR) instrument onboard Venus Express (Bertaux et al., 2007). It has a spectral resolution of about $\lambda/\Delta\lambda\sim 17000$ (Neefs et al., 2015) and during each solar occultation, NOMAD is able to sample the atmosphere acquiring sets of spectra at about 1 km tangent height step. An Acousto Optical Tunable Filter (AOTF) is used to select six diffraction orders measured quasi-simultaneously at every altitude. A detailed description of the NOMAD instrument was presented by Neefs et al. (2015) and its most recent instrumental characterization is summarized in Villanueva et al. (2022).

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The data processing and analysis performed at IAA-CSIC with NOMAD SO measurements have been extensively described in previous works (López-Valverde et al., 2023). The work presented here is focused on the cross-validation and statistical analysis of water vapor profiles, being the extension of the Part I (Brines, López-Valverde, Funke, Galindo, et al., 2025) devoted to the study of the water vapor climatology during 3 complete MYs. For that reason, for this work we used the same data set as in Part I, a sample of 7624 NOMAD solar occultations taken during MYs 34, 35, 36 and 37. These observations cover a Solar Longitude range from $L_S \sim 160^\circ$ of MY 34 to $L_S \sim 160^\circ$ of MY 37. These two papers build upon two previous studies of water vapor (Brines et al., 2023, 2024), but extending the data set and improving the data processing, retrieval scheme and vertical extension of the water vapor vertical profiles.

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As described in Part I, we used Level 1 calibrated transmittances (Trompet et al., 2023) from the latest pipeline processing at the Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy (BIRA-IASB), available at ESA (2024) and corrected from major systematics such as (i) a bending of the spectral continuum characterized with a fourth order polynomial, and (ii) a spectral shift. To perform this correction precisely, we used line-by-line forward model calculations carried out with the Karlsruhe OPTimized Radiative transfer Algorithm (KOPRA, Stiller (2000)). The cleaning of the NOMAD SO data has been extensively described in López-Valverde et al. (2023) and in Brines et al. (2023). The measurement noise provided by the official NOMAD calibration (Thomas et al., 2022) is improved by our in-house pre-processing pipeline by the characterization of covariance matrices (C-matrix). The diagonals of these matrices provide an estimation of the random component of the measurement noise, being 2-4 times smaller than the nominal one and improving the sensitivity of our retrievals at the uppermost atmosphere. The water vapor vertical profiles were obtained using the Retrieval Control Program (RCP, von Clarmann et al. (2003)) incorporating KOPRA as its Forward Model and using a first order Tikhonov regularization optimized for each diffraction order, applying a strong regularization at low altitudes with high dust optical depth. Similarly to Brines et al. (2023, 2024), the full vertical profiles were retrieved using a combination of two diffraction orders, 134 (3011-3035 cm^{-1}) or 136 (3056-3081 cm^{-1}) for the lower atmosphere (typically below 60 km) and 168 (3775-3805 cm^{-1}) or 169 (3798-3828 cm^{-1}) for the middle/upper atmosphere (above 60 km). We estimated the optimal transition altitude between orders for each occultation using the curve of growth of the strongest lines in orders 168 and 169 computed with KOPRA simulations. For the a priori atmosphere considered during the inversions, we used pressure and temperature profiles extracted from specific runs of MPCM (Forget et al., 1999) at the exact time and location of each solar occultation. The MPCM runs were performed taking into account the best estimate of the dust optical depths from Montabone et al. (2020) for each MY, including the GDS in MY 34. Due to the lack of measured data by the time the retrievals were performed, for MY 37 we used the same dust climatology than for MY 36. Since

Figure 1: Comparison of water vapor abundances presented in (Brines, López-Valverde, Funke, Galindo, et al., 2025) (this work, y -axis) with those obtained by (Fedorova et al., 2023) (x -axis). Colors indicate point density (a1, a2), Solar Longitude (b1, b2) and altitude (c1, c2) of the observations for the northern (left) and southern hemispheres (right). Red dashed line in top panels shows the linear fitting. Gray dashed line indicates $y = x$.

179 only the aphelion season of MY 37 is analyzed here, known to typically being clear from
 180 dust, we considered this approach to be appropriate.

181 3 NOMAD and ACS comparisons

182 Several teams within the TGO consortium are studying water vapor with different
 183 instruments onboard the spacecraft, characterizing topics such as the water at high altitudes
 184 (Belyaev et al., 2021; Brines et al., 2024), isotopic fractionation (Alday et al., 2021; Villanueva
 185 et al., 2022), water vapor saturation ratios (Fedorova et al., 2023) or water vapor seasonal
 186 variability (Aoki et al., 2022; Brines et al., 2023). In this Section we show a comparison
 187 of the results presented in Part I of this paper, referred to as SO-Brines25 within this
 188 section of the paper, with the results obtained from three of the most recent and extensive
 189 studies on water vapor performed with NOMAD (Aoki et al., 2022), hereafter referred
 190 to as SO-Aoki22, and ACS (Belyaev et al., 2021; Fedorova et al., 2023), hereafter referred
 191 to as MIR-Belyaev21 and NIR-Fedorova23 respectively. ACS, also onboard TGO, is a

Figure 2: Comparison of water vapor abundances presented in (Brines, López-Valverde, Funke, Galindo, et al., 2025) (this work, y -axis) with those obtained by (Aoki et al., 2022) (x -axis). Colors indicate point density (a1, a2), Solar Longitude (b1, b2) and altitude (c1, c2) of the observations for the northern (left) and southern hemispheres (right). Red dashed line in top panels shows the linear fitting. Gray dashed line indicates $y = x$.

192 suite of three high resolution spectrometers: (i) the near-infrared channel (NIR), (ii) the
 193 middle-infrared channel (MIR) and (iii) the thermal infra-red channel in honor of Professor
 194 Vassily Ivanovich Moroz (TIRVIM). This instrument operates in the spectral range from
 195 0.65 to 17 μm (Korablev et al., 2018) and like NOMAD, was designed to observe the atmosphere
 196 in solar occultation, nadir and limb geometries. The NIR channel, operating in the spectral
 197 range 0.73-1.6 μm , follows the design of the SPICAM-IR instrument, this is, based on
 198 an AOTF filter and an echelle-grating, entirely similar to the NOMAD SO channel.

199 In the case of SO and NIR channels, the pointing of both instrument is extremely
 200 similar during most of the atmospheric scans, making observations from both channels
 201 mostly collocated, besides some latidue-longitude variation at decimal precision. For this
 202 comparison analysis, we used those collocated scans, comparing only ACS NIR and NOMAD
 203 SO occultations within a latitude-longitude boxes of $5^\circ \times 5^\circ$. With this, we selected a
 204 subset of measurements during MYs 34, 35 and 36 resulting in a total of 936 vertical profiles
 205 common between SO-Brines25 and NIR-Fedorova23, making a total of 36416 coincident
 206 water vapor measurements. On the other hand, the profiles presented in Belyaev et al.
 207 (2021) measured with ACS MIR were obtained at totally different locations and times
 208 from those taken with NOMAD SO. Because of this limitation, we performed the comparison

209 between NOMAD SO and ACS MIR by averaging all profiles from MIR-Belyaev21 and
 210 SO-Brines25 measured within boxes of 10° latitude \times 30° longitude \times 30° in solar longitude.
 211 In addition, we imposed the criterion of comparing only profiles obtained at the same
 212 terminator, morning (from 1 am to 12 pm) or evening (from 12 pm to 12 am). With these
 213 restrictions we were able to obtain a total of 221 averaged profiles to compare. In the
 214 case of the data set from (Aoki et al., 2022), all water vapor vertical profiles were obtained
 215 with NOMAD SO, so the co-location criterion with SO-Brines25 is granted. The number
 216 of common occultations available for the comparison between the work presented here
 217 with SO-Aoki22 during MYs 34, 35 and 36 is 4197, making a total of 89901 coincident
 218 water vapor measurements.

219 Typically, the volume mixing ratios (VMR) used in studies of water vapor vertical
 220 profiles in Mars are expressed for a given reference atmosphere. So, in order to eliminate
 221 the effect of using different atmospheric densities in different retrieval schemes (GEM-
 222 Mars in the case of SO-Aoki22, and the MPCM in our inversion), the VMR from SO-
 223 Aoki22 and NIR-Fedorova23 data sets were scaled computing new VMRs using the total
 224 atmospheric density from SO-Brines25 as reference. Hence, the scaled VMRs used for
 225 these comparisons are defined as $\text{VMR}^A = \rho_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^A / \rho_{\text{TOT}}^B$ and $\text{VMR}^F = \rho_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^F / \rho_{\text{TOT}}^B$,
 226 where ρ_{TOT}^B is the total atmospheric density from SO-Brines25 and $\rho_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^A$, $\rho_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^F$ are the
 227 retrieved water vapor number density from SO-Aoki22 and NIR-Fedorova23 respectively.
 228 For the comparison with MIR-Belyaev21 we focused the analysis on absolute water vapor
 229 number density instead of VMR.

230 The procedures and retrieval methodology used in SO-Brines25 and those used in
 231 the rest of data sets are all different, each one of them requiring specific assumptions to
 232 consider during the inversions. Therefore, the comparison presented here must be taken
 233 with caution. The data analysis and inversion methods performed by each team are described
 234 in Aoki et al. (2022); Belyaev et al. (2021) and Fedorova et al. (2023) for SO-Aoki22, MIR-
 235 Belyaev21 and NIR-Fedorova23 retrievals respectively. In Figures 1 and 2 we show correlograms
 236 with the comparison between the results obtained in SO-Brines25 (this work, y -axis) and
 237 those from NIR-Fedorova23 and SO-Aoki22 respectively (x -axis). Left and right panels
 238 indicate measurements from the northern and southern hemispheres respectively. For
 239 both Figures, colors in top panels show the point density distribution (the more yellowish,
 240 the larger number of points) whereas the colors in the middle and bottom panels represent
 241 the solar longitude and the altitude of the observations respectively. Overall the agreement
 242 is good in both comparisons, with mean correlation factors of 0.92 for the comparison
 243 with NIR-Fedorova23 and 0.83 in the case of SO-Aoki22. A linear fit of the comparison
 244 also shows an excellent agreement between the three sets of retrievals, considering the
 245 large differences in the retrieval approaches. Nevertheless, we notice that the results presented
 246 in this work are globally about $\sim 7.5\%$ larger than SO-Aoki22 and about $\sim 11\%$ system-
 247 atically smaller than NIR-Fedorova23, values which fall within the retrieval's uncertainties
 248 of both NOMAD and ACS. Although the data set was different, it is worth to mention
 249 the improvement observed since the previous NOMAD-NOMAD comparison exercise presented
 250 in Brines et al. (2023), where they reported $\sim 13\%$ larger water vapor abundances than
 251 those from Aoki et al. (2022).

252 Despite the overall good agreement, Figures 1 and 2 show some profiles with systematic
 253 bias. The comparison with NIR-Fedorova23 reveals a diverging branch toward higher abundances
 254 retrieved from ACS NIR during the aphelion season in the southern hemisphere, as shown
 255 in Figure 1-b2. In addition, this bias seems to appear systematically at altitudes about
 256 50-60 km, which for this season and hemisphere, might correspond with the top most
 257 retrieved altitude suggesting border effects during the inversion being a possible reason
 258 of this discrepancy. The comparison with SO-Aoki22, on the other hand, reveals a diverging
 259 branch towards higher water abundances in SO-Brines25 results in the northern hemisphere
 260 and another towards higher VMR values in SO-Aoki22 results in the southern hemisphere.
 261 As shown in Figure 2-b1, this first branch corresponds with profiles measured during the

262 aphelion season at low altitudes below 20-30 km as shown in Figure 2-c1. Similarly, in
 263 the southern hemisphere the observed bias also occurs at low altitudes during the aphelion,
 264 but in this case showing a deficit in SO-Brines25 abundances. The reason of these bias
 265 could be related to several factors. At those altitudes, the constraints imposed during
 266 the inversion, i.e. regularization, play a significant role and values obtained at the lowermost
 267 edge of the retrieved altitude grid might be affected by the a priori climatology, which
 268 in our case is known to overestimate water vapor abundance during the northern summer
 269 as discussed in Section 4. Other possible reason for the discrepancies could be the retrieval
 270 method itself. In the case of SO-Aoki22, the assumption of a constant VMR along the
 271 LOS and not considering the contribution of the spectra from the layers above the observation
 272 shall introduce biases under conditions of strong vertical gradients, which are common
 273 at low altitudes during the northern summer. This discrepancy was previously noticed
 274 and discussed in Brines et al. (2024) (see their Supporting Information document).

Figure 3: Comparison of water vapor volume mixing ratio vertical profiles retrieved from NOMAD (blue, green) and ACS (red) observations. The locations (longitude, latitude) of NOMAD and ACS observations are indicated in blue and red respectively. Season (L_S) and local time (LST) of indicated in black. Dashed line shows the water vapor volume mixing ratio extracted from the MPCM at the NOMAD locations.

275 In order to complement this comparison, a selection of 32 sets of profiles, 16 for each
 276 hemisphere at a wide variety of latitudes and measured during different seasons are presented
 277 in Figures S1 and S2 on the SI document for the northern and southern hemispheres respectively.

278 A smaller sample of four sets of profiles is shown in Figure 3. This set was selected because
 279 it captures an assortment of representative features observed in the water vapor profiles,
 280 covering different atmospheric conditions, from low to high water vapor abundance. Each
 281 panel shows the retrieved profiles from SO-Brines25 (blue, this work), SO-Aoki22 (green)
 282 and NIR-Fedorova23 (red). Overall, as discussed above in this Section, the agreement
 283 between the three retrievals is good, with all three profiles capturing the same vertical
 284 structures. However, some discrepancies arise regarding the amplitude of those structures,
 285 with more pronounced features appearing in SO-Brines25 as illustrated in Figures 3-b
 286 and 3-d. The reason of these differences might be due to the different vertical resolution
 287 obtained during the inversions, i.e. the width of the averaging kernels, which are directly
 288 related with the information content and is affected by the regularization imposed during
 289 the inversions. Our retrievals seem optimal in terms of vertical resolution, and as discussed
 290 in Part I, since the objective of our study was to provide a global water vapor climatology,
 291 our regularization common for all the retrievals was fine tuned to provide reliable results
 292 on a wide variety of atmospheric scenarios. In addition, the noise propagation is comparable
 293 or better than in the other inversions, and the altitude coverage that can be studied is
 294 also larger.

Figure 4: Comparison of water vapor number density vertical profiles retrieved from ACS MIR and NOMAD SO at four longitude-latitude- L_S windows. For each set of three panels, left panel shows the water vapor vertical profiles from NOMAD (blue) and ACS (red). When more than one observation falls within the window, thin lines show the individual profiles while thick line shows the averaged profile. Middle panel shows the ratio between the averaged NOMAD and ACS profiles, and right panel shows the geographic location of the NOMAD (blue) and ACS (red) observations. Thin dots show the location of all observations while thick dots show the location of the observations within the window. Vertical and horizontal gray lines indicate the limits of the longitude-latitude window.

295 As described at the beginning of this section, NOMAD SO and ACS MIR observations
 296 are not collocated. Hence, in order to compare with this instrument we decided to perform
 297 averages with the water vapor vertical profiles retrieved at specific boxes of latitude
 298 and longitude. Then, we computed the ratio between those averages. A selection
 299 of four cases is shown in Figure 4. Since variations on the location and timing of the observations
 300 imply possible variations on the thermal structure of the atmosphere and on the water
 301 vertical distribution, some vertical features on the water vapor profile are observed by

Figure 5: Ratios of averaged SO-Brines25 vertical profiles with averaged MIR-Belyaev21 profiles within boxes of 10° latitude \times 30° longitude \times 30° in solar longitude, computed for MYs 34 (a), MY 35 (b) and MY 36 (c). Thin blue and red lines indicate the ratio during morning and evening observations respectively. Thick lines show the mean ratio. Vertical black dashed line indicates the ratio equal 1. Gray shaded area indicates the dispersion of the average of all profiles.

302 one instrument but not by the other, revealing "spikes" on the ratio profiles. These "spikes"
 303 are observed at a wide variety of altitudes and did not revealed systematic biases at any
 304 specific atmospheric layer, as shown in Figure 5 when all ratios are put together. This
 305 is true for MYs 35, 36 and MY 34 below 90 km ($>10^{-3}$ mbar) which shows larger ACS
 306 water vapor abundances than NOMAD at high altitudes (Figure 5-a). Although perhaps
 307 this discrepancy could be due to boundary constrains during the retrievals, this feature
 308 is different to that observed in the comparison with ACS NIR which showed a similar
 309 bias at the top most altitudes during the aphelion season, not the perihelion season as
 310 observed in the comparison with ACS MIR. Nevertheless, besides this discrepancy in MY
 311 34 and taking into account that a profile-by-profile comparison is not possible between
 312 these two instruments due to non collocated measurements, both datasets show qualitative
 313 a global good agreement, both capturing the same water vapor seasonal trends.

314 4 NOMAD and MPCM comparisons

315 4.1 Seasonal variability

316 Global circulation models (GCMs) are essential tools to provide a complete and
 317 detailed understanding of the atmospheric dynamics and climate. Although physics are
 318 the core of these models, real observations are required in order to improve, fine tune
 319 and validate the picture drawn by the pure theoretical assumptions made during the elaboration
 320 of the GCMs. For that purpose, here we provide a first comparison of the NOMAD SO
 321 dataset presented in Part I (Brines, López-Valverde, Funke, González-Galindo, et al., 2025)
 322 with the Laboratoire de Météorologie Dynamique (LMD) Mars Planetary Climate Model
 323 (MPCM, (Forget et al., 1999)).

Figure 6: Absolute difference of water vapor volume mixing ratio $\Delta\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ between NOMAD SO and the MPCM over Solar Longitude during MYs 34, 35, 36 and 37 for the Northern (c) and Southern (d) hemispheres. Top two panels show the $\Delta\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ at 30 km (a) and 80 km (b) as a function of latitude and Solar Longitude. All panels use the same color scheme. Blue colors indicate larger MPCM abundances than NOMAD.

324 In Figure 6 we show the absolute difference $\Delta\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{NOMAD}} - \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{M-PCM}}$ between
 325 the NOMAD SO ($\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{NOMAD}}$) and the M-PCM ($\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{M-PCM}}$) water vapor volume mixing ratio
 326 from the second half of MY 34 to the first half of MY 37. In order to provide a meaningful
 327 analysis, the water vapor vertical profiles from the MPCM have been produced for the
 328 exact location and time as those obtained from the NOMAD SO observations. Top panels
 329 (a) and (b) show the latitude and differences averaged in altitude windows of 5 km centered
 330 at 30 and 80 km respectively, in both cases within boxes of 5° in latitude and 5° in solar
 331 longitude. In panels (c) and (d), the differences between measured and simulated vertical
 332 profiles are shown in bins of 1° in solar longitude. In all these panels from Figure 6, reddish
 333 colors indicate larger values of water vapor abundance (VMR) observed with NOMAD
 334 whereas blueish hues indicate larger values in the MPCM. The color scheme of this figure
 335 has been defined in order to emphasize differences at least larger than $|\Delta\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}| =$
 336 10 ppm and by making this map showing absolute differences we are highlighting the observed-
 337 modeled discrepancies during periods of large water vapor abundance, this is, perihelion
 338 season and low altitudes during northern summer season. An additional figure showing

339 relative differences defined as $\delta\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = (\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{NOMAD}} - \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{M-PCM}}) / \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{M-PCM}}$ is shown in Figure
340 S3 of SI document.

341 From Figures 6-a and 6-b, and focusing the analysis on MYs 35 and 36 (two complete
342 MYs), MPCM seems to underestimate water vapor abundance at low altitudes, particularly
343 during $L_S=240^\circ-360^\circ$ in the southern hemisphere. This effect is also noticeable in Figure
344 S3-a of SI, where larger NOMAD water vapor abundances are observed at 30 km in the
345 aphelion season during $L_S=0^\circ-150^\circ$ at both hemispheres. In contrast, at high altitudes,
346 MPCM systematically overestimates water vapor abundance almost during the whole
347 year with some exceptions at $L_S\sim 120^\circ$ at both hemispheres as shown in Figure S3-b, and
348 during $L_S=260^\circ-300^\circ$, shown in Figure 6-b. The first could be due to an underestimation
349 of the modeled global circulation, which seems to be actually more intense according to
350 the larger water vapor abundances observed by NOMAD at all latitudes. This underestimation
351 of the model, however, only appears above 30 km altitude. Below this altitude the model
352 is overestimated, a feature observed during the whole aphelion season in the northern
353 hemisphere. The second exception mentioned above corresponds with the perihelion water
354 vapor pumping in the southern hemisphere analyzed by Brines et al. (2024) and could
355 be due again to a deficient vertical transport of water vapor in the model at high southern
356 latitudes.

357 Looking at the left hand side of Figure 6 (all panels), the presence of blue hues during
358 almost the whole My 34 in both hemispheres is evident, suggesting that MPCM overestimates
359 water vapor abundance during MY 34's GDS and its decay phase. This overestimation
360 is observed throughout the whole vertical range analyzed here, with the exception of a
361 short period of underestimated abundances below 40 km during $L_S \sim 260^\circ$ in the northern
362 hemisphere. Looking at the aphelion season ($L_S=0^\circ-180^\circ$) of MYs 35,36 and 37, particularly
363 at mid-low northern latitudes and at low altitudes below 30 km (Figure 6-c), water vapor
364 abundances are systematically larger in the MPCM. Besides this low altitude aphelion
365 overestimation, interestingly only a short period during MY 37 ($L_S \sim 120^\circ$) shows a
366 strong underestimation of water vapor VMR with the model, suggesting and observed
367 rare water vapor injection up to 50 km altitude at latitudes $50^\circ\text{N}-60^\circ\text{N}$ not simulated
368 in the MPCM.

369 In contrast to the aphelion, the perihelion season shows a different pattern in the
370 seasonal and vertical distribution of the differences between model and NOMAD SO measurements.
371 In this case, during the period ranging $L_S = 240^\circ-300^\circ$, the overestimation in the model
372 appears at 40-80 km altitude in the northern hemisphere whereas the opposite (NOMAD
373 water vapor larger than MPCM) occurs below 40 km altitude in the northern hemisphere
374 and systematically at almost the whole vertical range in the southern hemisphere, evidencing
375 difficulties in the model to reproduce the southern's summer water enhancement. In addition,
376 at $L_S \sim 270^\circ$ MPCM underestimates water vapor abundance at 100 km altitude in the
377 northern hemisphere. This water vapor enhancement observed by NOMAD and not reproduced
378 in the model, as mentioned above, could be related with the plumes observed in the southern
379 hemisphere (Brines et al., 2024). This pattern, similarly observed in both MYs 35 and
380 36, suggests not only a more efficient vertical transport of water vapor in the southern
381 hemisphere than the model predicts but also that the meridional transport in the MPCM
382 could be overestimated at 40-80 km while underestimated at altitudes as high as 100 km.
383 This difficulty in reproducing the distinct water vapor increase in the southern hemisphere
384 during the perihelion was also reported by (Vals et al., 2022), who attributed the issue
385 to the difficulty of the model to reproduce the true dust vertical distribution.

386 4.2 Latitudinal variability

387 In addition to the seasonal variability study discussed above, we performed a latitudinal
388 variability analysis with MPCM simulations, similar to that presented in Part I with NOMAD
389 SO observations. The differences on the latitudinal distribution between observations

390 and simulations are shown in Figures 7 and 8 for the aphelion (from $L_S = 0^\circ$ to $L_S =$
 391 180°) and perihelion (from $L_S = 0^\circ$ to $L_S = 180^\circ$) seasons respectively. As done in
 392 Part I, we selected different subsets of observations/simulations during relatively small
 393 ranges of L_S ($\Delta L_S = 30^\circ$). For a given latitude, in order to avoid mixing different local
 394 times, we split the sets considering occultations from only one terminator, at the morning
 395 (top two rows) and at the evening (bottom two rows). We present the relative difference
 396 between NOMAD SO observations and their corresponding MPCM simulations within
 397 those L_S windows assuming that the observed distribution is caused mainly by the latitudinal
 398 variability. Here, the vertical profiles were averaged in 5° latitude bins. For each L_S window,
 399 observations and simulations from MYs 35, 36 were used to compute the latitudinal distribution.

Figure 7: Multi-annual average of the latitudinal distribution of the relative differences $\delta\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ between NOMAD SO and MPCM water vapor volume mixing ratio (VMR) during the aphelion season from observations at the morning terminator (top two rows from a1 to a6) and evening terminator (bottom two rows from b1 to b6). Blue colors indicate larger MPCM abundances than NOMAD.

400 During the beginning of the MY from $L_S = 0^\circ$ to $L_S = 30^\circ$ in solar longitude,
 401 different behaviors are observed at both terminators. In Figure 7-a1 for the morning observations,

Figure 8: Multi-annual average of the latitudinal distribution of the relative differences $\delta\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ between NOMAD SO and MPCM water vapor volume mixing ratio (VMR) during the perihelion season from observations at the morning terminator (top two rows from a1 to a6) and evening terminator (bottom two rows from b1 to b6). Blue colors indicate larger MPCM abundances than NOMAD.

402 the model shows a region of excess of water vapor below 20 km altitude at both hemispheres
 403 followed by a layer with deficit of water at 20-40 km . In contrast, during the evening
 404 and shown in Figure 7-b1, the region showing lower abundances in the model than in
 405 the NOMAD observations extends from 5 to 60 km. However, in both cases, water vapor
 406 is systematically overestimated in the MPMC above 60 km altitude, pattern which repeats
 407 itself until $L_S = 90^\circ$. As the northern spring advances a clear interhemispheric asymmetry
 408 arises below 40 km, with MPCM highly overestimating water vapor abundance at low
 409 altitudes in the northern hemisphere as shown in Figures 7-a2, 7-a3, 7-b1. This feature
 410 remains constant for the rest of the season, being the region between 40-60 km the one
 411 presenting more variability. Another interesting discrepancy between model and NOMAD
 412 measurements can be observed by the end of the aphelion season during $L_S = 120^\circ$

413 to $L_S = 180^\circ$, period when the northern hemisphere above 20 km seems to be more
 414 humid than the MPCM predicts and illustrated in Figures 7-a5, 7-a6, 7-b5 and 7-b6.

415 As shown in Figures 8-a1 this same situation is maintained during $L_S = 180^\circ$ -
 416 210° at the morning. However, as the southern summer approaches, the picture changes
 417 and the differences NOMAD-MPCM reveal a strong deficit in the water vapor abundance
 418 simulated in the southern hemisphere. By $L_S = 240^\circ$ - 270° , although the agreement
 419 between model and observations is good below 60 km at mid latitudes as shown in Figures
 420 8-a3 and 8-b3, the model underestimation at high southern latitudes becomes progressively
 421 more relevant. During $L_S = 270^\circ - 300^\circ$, larger water vapor abundances reaching
 422 altitudes as high as 100 km are observed in NOMAD profiles. This structures, or plumes,
 423 were known to not be properly reproduced in the MPCM, as previously disused in Brines
 424 et al. (2024). In addition, in Figure 8-a4 it is clear the connection of the strong water
 425 vapor injection in the southern hemisphere with the layer of underestimated water vapor
 426 in the model at 100 km altitude in the northern hemisphere. It is also interesting to highlight
 427 the differences observed during this period at ~ 60 km in the northern hemisphere, clearly
 428 visible in Figures 8-a4 and 8-b4 and being particularly more intense at the morning.

429 4.3 Statistical comparison

430 Besides the analysis focused on the seasonal and latitudinal variability, it is convenient
 431 to study the global correlation between both the model and the observations in order
 432 to provide a general view of the agreement/discrepancies. For that reason, in Figure 9
 433 we show a series of correlograms of the water vapor VMR as observed by NOMAD (μ_{NOMAD})
 434 in the x -axis and that modeled by the MPCM (μ_{MPCM}) in the y -axis. For each MY and
 435 in order to provide a meaningful picture of the comparison, we repeated the scatter plot
 436 coloring different magnitudes such as the density of points (panels a), the solar longitude
 437 (panel b), the latitude and longitude of the measurements (panels c and d), the local solar
 438 time (panel e) and the altitudes (panel f). In order to highlight the region of 0-100 ppm,
 439 a set of figures showing these same panels but in logarithmic scale is presented in the
 440 SI document.

441 From Figure 9-a1 to 9-f1 for MY 34, we observe water vapor abundances system-
 442 atically larger in the MPCM. Particularly, abundances at high altitudes between 100-120
 443 km are highly overestimated in MPCM, observed in the form of reddish branches in Figure
 444 9-f1. During this MY, unlike the following years, a clear structure with higher density
 445 of points can be observed around $\mu_{\text{MPCM}}=100$ -150 ppm (Figure 9-a1) corresponding mostly
 446 with observations in the southern hemisphere at mid-low altitudes between 30-50 km during
 447 the decay phase of the GDS ($L_S=220^\circ$ - 260°). Corresponding with the peak of the GDS
 448 during $L_S=180^\circ$ - 200° , another structure can be observed at $\mu_{\text{MPCM}} \sim 200$ ppm. Interestingly,
 449 its horizontal shape and color gradient shown in Figure 9-f1 suggests more vertical variability
 450 in NOMAD than in MPCM, the later producing similarly large water vapor abundances
 451 at every altitude.

452 For MYs 35 and 36 the situation is slightly different. As previously discussed, although
 453 there are some discrepancies between model and observations during specific periods and
 454 altitude regions, in this case the overall agreement seems qualitative better than in MY
 455 34. During these two MYs showing similar structures are noticeable (Figures 9-a2 to 9-
 456 f2 for MY 35 and 9-a3 to 9-f3 for MY 36). As shown in these figures and clearly visible
 457 in log-scale (Figures S4 and S5 from SI), multiple horizontal branches are observed during
 458 the whole year with no clear correlation with the latitude or local time of the observations.
 459 In contrast, when looking at the altitude distribution of these structures (Figures S4-f2
 460 and S5-f3) and similarly to what is observed during MY 34, it is evident the tendency
 461 of the MPCM on sustaining higher water vapor abundances at higher altitudes.

462 At last, for the MY 37 (Figure 9-a4 to 9-f4), systematically higher abundances are
 463 observed in MPCM during $L_S=150^\circ$ - 180° at both hemispheres. In contrast and unlike

Figure 9: Comparison of NOMAD SO water vapor abundances (x -axis) with those simulated by the MPCM (y -axis) for MYs 34 (panels a1 to f1), 35 (panels a2 to f2), 36 (panels a3 to f3) and 37 (panels a4 to f4). For each MY, colors in panels a to f indicate the density of measurements (panel a), solar longitude (panel b), latitude and longitude (panels c and d), local solar time (panel e) and altitude (panel f). Gray dashed line indicates $y = x$.

464 previous years, a population of larger NOMAD abundances is observed around $L_S \sim 120^\circ$
 465 in the northern hemisphere (Figures 9-b4, 9-c4, S5-b4 and S5-c4) mostly below 50 km
 466 altitude (Figures 9-f4 and S5-f4). Finally, and common in the four MYs analyzed here,
 467 we do not observe any correlation of excess/defect of water vapor abundance in the model
 468 with the longitude of the observations (Figure 9-d1, 9-d2, 9-d3 and 9-d4), suggesting the
 469 zonal distribution of water being properly reproduced in the model.

470 Besides this analysis, it is important to note the coupling of solar longitude, latitude
 471 and local time of the NOMAD observations due the orbital geometry of TGO. This imposes
 472 a strong restriction on the location and time of the observations, forcing some latitudes

Figure 9: (continued)

473 to be sampled only during specific times and seasons. Nevertheless, this potential observational
 474 bias is overcome by the large amount of measurements during different years analyzed
 475 here, successfully filling the gaps left by the orbital geometry during individual years.

476 5 Cluster analysis

477 The water vapor distribution on Mars has a strong variability with season and latitude,
 478 although it follows repeated patterns and similar vertical structures every MY. Therefore,
 479 a characterization by means of a small set of representative profiles could be very useful
 480 to characterize the water vapor climatology. In this Section we present the results obtained
 481 after the application of cluster analysis techniques to our retrieved data set of profiles
 482 in order to identify the most relevant vertical structures associated to different seasons
 483 and locations. Cluster analysis is a statistical method used to categorize similar objects
 484 into groups, or "clusters," ensuring that objects within the same cluster are more similar
 485 to each other than to those in different groups. The main objective of cluster analysis
 486 is to reveal the inherent groupings in a data set without any prior knowledge about the
 487 subsets. There are several techniques for clustering, each with distinct advantages and
 488 limitations. For this work, and based on previous similar studies on Martian temperature
 489 vertical profiles Cala Hurtado (2016), we used the K-means algorithm. This is an iterative
 490 method which clusters data minimizing the distance between data points within a given
 491 cluster while maximizing the mean distance between clusters. First, a number of clusters
 492 is provided. Then, a representative vertical profile for each cluster is randomly defined,
 493 i.e. centroid, and the retrieved NOMAD profiles are assigned to each one of those clusters
 494 in a way that the mean euclidean distance between each profile and the cluster's centroid
 495 is minimum. After that, the centroids are recalculated for the new clusters and the assignation
 496 process is done again. These two steps are repeated until convergence, that is, until the
 497 difference between the new centroids and the previous one is less than a certain value.
 498 Here we explored different initial configurations and several numbers of clusters, from
 499 2 to 20, in order to evaluate the impact of the random initialization of centroids and the
 500 sensitivity to different levels of clustering. We studied several quality metrics commonly
 501 used in this kind of studies such as the Silhouette coefficient Rousseeuw (1987), the Davies-
 502 Bouldin index Davies and Bouldin (1979) or the Calinski-Harabasz index Caliński and
 503 Harabasz (1974). All these metrics try to evaluate and compare the between-cluster separation
 504 with the within-cluster dispersion, where the larger the first and the smaller the second,
 505 the better. After these tests and based on visual inspections, we decided to use $K =$
 506 6 clusters to provide a simplified view of the water vapor climatology, describing the seasonal
 507 and latitudinal inter-annual variability with 6 distinct representative profiles. We applied
 508 the clustering to the whole data set at once, including the four MYs and both southern
 509 and northern hemisphere measurements during the cluster assignation.

510 In Figure 10, we show the results of the clustering for MYs 34, 35, 36 and 37. Left
 511 panels indicate the latitude and solar longitude of each identified group, labeled with a
 512 different color for each MY. The representative profiles of each cluster are presented in
 513 the right hand side panel. From Figure 10 we can identify different features represented
 514 by distinct groups.

- 515 • First, Group 0 is observed during $L_S \sim 0^\circ - 180^\circ$ and $L_S \sim 340^\circ - 360^\circ$ and includes
 516 all the profiles representative for the aphelion season and the northern spring equinox.
 517 It shows low and nearly constant water vapor abundance at all altitudes and is
 518 common during this period in all MYs. On the other hand, groups 1 to 5 are used
 519 to describe the variability during the perihelion season.
- 520 • Group 1, characterized by abundances about 100 ppm below 50 km, appears scattered
 521 during the second half of the year, although seems to be more common in the southern
 522 hemisphere. It is particularly frequent during $L_S \sim 200^\circ - 250^\circ$ in MY 34, period
 523 which coincides with the decay phase of the GDS. It is also common around $L_S \sim 320^\circ$

Figure 10: Left panels show the seasonal-latitudinal distribution of the retrieved NOMAD SO water vapor vertical profiles for MYs 34, 35, 36 and 37 (from top to bottom respectively). Colors indicate the clusters where profiles were assigned. Right panel shows the representative water vapor VMR vertical profile of each cluster.

- 524 in MYs 34, 35, 36 coinciding with the appearance of C-storms at the end of each
 525 MY.
- 526 • Group 2, with abundances between 50 to 100 ppm below 40 km, is common at mid-
 527 high northern latitudes below 70°. Unlike any other year, this profile appears also
 528 during the aphelion of MY 37 at $L_S \sim 110^\circ - 120^\circ$.
 - 529 • Group 3 shows abundances ranging between 100 to 200 ppm below 50 km and about
 530 50 ppm above 80 km. It appears only in the southern hemisphere (mid latitudes)
 531 and is common during $L_S \sim 250^\circ - 280^\circ$ in MYs 34,35,36. This period corresponds
 532 with the perihelion and its time and location of appearance coincides with the detection
 533 of high water vapor abundance in the upper atmosphere, as discussed by (Belyaev
 534 et al., 2021), and more recently by (Brines et al., 2024).
 - 535 • Group 4, with abundances above 100 ppm below 45 km and with a sharp decrease
 536 above, appears scattered in both hemispheres, usually acting as a transition between
 537 groups 1, 2 and 3.
 - 538 • Finally, Group 5 represents water vapor profiles with abundances of about 200 ppm
 539 below 60 km and about 50 ppm at 80 km, decreasing with altitude. This type of
 540 profiles appears at $L_S \sim 180^\circ - 210^\circ$ in MY 34 and are representative of the peak
 541 activity of the GDS during that year. This group is also briefly observed during
 542 the perihelion at $L_S \sim 260^\circ$ in MYs 35 and 36 and $L_S \sim 280^\circ$ in MY 34, between
 543 observations of the Group 3.

544 These results show that seasonal variability is overall more relevant than the latitudinal
 545 or local time variations. However, some groups may have a preference to appear in the
 546 northern or southern hemispheres, and similarly, a few groups were observed more frequently
 547 during specific local times.

Figure 11: Left panel shows the number of profiles measured at the northern (red) and southern (blue) hemisphere for each group. Right panel shows the same but for profiles measured during mornings (blue) and evenings (red).

548 In Figure 11 we show the number of NOMAD SO observations grouped in each cluster,
 549 indicating if the profiles within the group correspond to measurements taken at the northern
 550 or southern hemisphere (left panel) and if the observations correspond to the morning
 551 or evening terminators (right panel). Although some of these groups were observed with
 552 a slightly larger frequency in one hemisphere than in the other, only Groups 1 and 3 stand
 553 out clearly to be representative for the southern hemisphere. While the first corresponds
 554 to the observations during the decay phase of the GDS, the second represents profiles
 555 showing the largest abundance of water vapor at high altitudes. On the other hand, Group
 556 2 seems to be more frequent in the northern hemisphere during the winter solstice. Regarding
 557 the local time, profiles from Groups 3 and 4 appear more repeatedly during evening observations.
 558 However, the larger amount of evening profiles in Group 5, which contains mostly profiles
 559 observed during the GDS, is due to the fact that this event was observed only during
 560 evenings indicating a bias in the sample rather than a true feature.

561 For completion, in Figure 12 we show the result of repeating the clustering exercise
 562 with water vapor vertical profiles extracted from the MPCM. Here we observe a similar
 563 seasonal pattern as that obtained with NOMAD observations, with a Group 0 characterized
 564 by low water vapor abundances dominating the aphelion season, a specific Group 5 representative
 565 for the MY 34 GDS and a wide variety of profiles during the second half of each MY. In
 566 this case, in contrast with the clustering from NOMAD, the latitudinal and seasonal correlations
 567 with the different groups seem more evident due to the less variability produced by the
 568 model.

- 569 • Group 1, similarly to the NOMAD clustering, is particularly frequent in the southern
 570 hemisphere during $L_S \sim 200^\circ - 250^\circ$ in MY 34, corresponding with the decay phase
 571 of the GDS. Then, it has a repeated appearance at $50^\circ\text{S} - 60^\circ\text{S}$ at $L_S = 240^\circ$
- 572 • Group 2 is mainly observed at mid-high latitudes, typically above 50° in both hemispheres
 573 during $L_S \sim 200^\circ - 330^\circ$ with some excursions to low southern latitudes at the end
 574 of MYs 35 and 36.
- 575 • Group 3 is dominant at the perihelion, around $L_S \sim 240^\circ$ mainly in the southern
 576 hemisphere, although during MY 34 is also abundant in the northern one.
- 577 • Group 4, in this case, is more abundant at latitudes below 50° in both hemispheres,
 578 being particularly frequent during $L_S = 180^\circ - 210^\circ$ and $L_S = 270^\circ - 300^\circ$ for MYs 35
 579 and 36 and during $L_S = 300^\circ - 360^\circ$ for MY 34

Figure 12: Left panels show the seasonal-latitudinal distribution of the Mars-PCM water vapor vertical profiles for MYs 34, 35, 36 and 37 (from top to bottom respectively). Colors indicate the clusters where profiles were assigned. Right panel shows the representative water vapor VMR vertical profile of each cluster.

580 What is also interesting from this analysis, with both NOMAD and MPCM clustering,
 581 is the extremely similar climatology observed during the perihelion of MYs 35 and 36
 582 and the strong contrast with the same season in MY 34. This evidences once again the
 583 impact of global dust storms on the water vapor global distribution (Aoki et al., 2019;
 584 Brines et al., 2023; Fedorova et al., 2020). In addition, it is worth noting the strong difference
 585 of the clusters obtained from the MPCM with those obtained from NOMAD at high altitudes.
 586 Above 60 km, the gradient observed in the clusters from NOMAD is noticeably larger
 587 than those observed in the MPCM clusters. This fact highlights once again the system-
 588 atically wetter atmosphere produced by the model particularly during and after the GDS
 589 and during the perihelion the northern hemisphere.

590 In order to extend the cluster analysis further, we performed two additional tests.
 591 First, as illustrated in Figures 10 and 12, applying the clustering algorithm to the water
 592 vapor VMR profiles directly in ppm units provides a climatology more sensitive to the
 593 perihelion season. In contrast the aphelion season is characterized basically by one common
 594 profile of low abundances. To address that complication, we applied the clustering not
 595 to the VMR profiles but to their logarithm. This way the grouping was more sensitive
 596 to profiles of low water vapor abundance. The results of this additional test are shown
 597 in Figures S6 and S7 of SI. Although some sensitivity was lost at the perihelion, more
 598 groups were assigned to the aphelion season revealing distinct groups representative of
 599 specific latitudes during the first half of the MYs that were missing with the clustering
 600 previously discussed. Secondly, in order to look for possible anomalies or issues during
 601 the retrieval process, we run the clustering assignation with 20 clusters. After doing this
 602 exercise we did not find any cluster to be representative of potentially wrong or anomalous
 603 profiles.

6 Discussion

6.1 Cross-validation within TGO

Cross-validation is an essential task in remote sensing measurements, such as those made by TGO, to verify the robustness and reliability of the results. The comparison presented in this work, taking into account instrumental uncertainties and differences in data processing, retrieval methods, and vertical resolution/information content, revealed an overall good agreement between teams and instruments. This is illustrated and quantified with the good correlation factors obtained in the two comparisons SO-Brines25 - SO-Aoki22 and SO-Brines25 - NIR-Fedorova23, of 0.83 and 0.91 respectively. Nevertheless, some discrepancies in the SO-Brines25 - SO-Aoki22 comparison are observed, mostly during the aphelion season, which correspond to biases on the high water vapor abundances at low altitudes. This is a well known discrepancy to the two teams involved in this comparison (Brines et al., 2024) and is due to the very different retrieval approaches. Our SO-Brines25 inversion follows a global fit approach and is therefore less sensitive to the vertical gradients expected at those altitudes during this season. The comparison with NIR-Fedorova23 revealed some biases also during the aphelion season but only at the top-most altitude of the water vapor profiles in the southern hemisphere. Our water vapor are a factor 5 lower, possibly as a result of our inversion being less sensitive to the apriori, which shows larger abundances at the top most edge of the profiles. A similar bias is also observed in the comparison with ACS MIR during the perihelion season of MY 34, with systematically lower water vapor abundances in our dataset above 90-100 km. In addition, in the case of MIR we observed discrepancies in the form of sudden changes in the water vapor density at a specific altitude. It is important to remind here that, in contrast to NIR, MIR and NOMAD SO observations are not exactly coincident. Hence, this differences in the vertical structure observed in some water vapor profiles are possibly due to differences on the thermal vertical structure leading to supersaturation and condensation processes. These features, captured by one instrument but not by the other, suggest the aforementioned processes to be extremely local and differences in timing/location of the observations are relevant to properly detect these events. Nevertheless, besides these discrepancies at specific altitudes due to the different locations and local times of the compared profiles, globally both datasets show similar seasonal trends on the water vapor vertical distribution.

6.2 Comparison with the MPCM

It is well known that modeling the Martian water cycle is extremely complex, with many atmospheric variables and processes directly or indirectly affecting it. These include factors such as water ice micro-physics affecting the condensation/sublimation of water, or the dust injection and distribution, able to modify the atmospheric thermal structure and hence affecting the vertical transport of water vapor (Montmessin et al., 2017; Urata et al., 2025). The differences analyzed here are considered relevant and non dependent on the specific run of the MPCM used in this work (SVN3323, config. MCD6) and may therefore be taken into account for future improvements of the water cycle modeling. One of the most striking discrepancies between the model and the NOMAD measurements is observed during MY 34. As a result of the MY 34's GDS and the enhanced dust abundances and temperatures, large water vapor abundances are observed as high as 80 km (Aoki et al., 2019; Brines et al., 2023; Fedorova et al., 2020). Although the MPCM effectively produces an enhancement during MY 34, its intensity and duration are way larger than what it is observed, producing a systematic overestimation of the water abundances almost at almost all altitudes and during the whole year. This may be due to not only a not well reproduced dust vertical distribution, but also to the warmer temperatures observed in the model (Vals et al., 2022). Besides these differences due to the uniqueness of the GDS event, other discrepancies seem to be repeated every season. During the aphelion season, i.e. the first half of the MY, the excess of water vapor observed in the model at low altitudes, where the bulk of water vapor is located during this season, suggests the MPCM to have

Figure 13: -PROVISIONAL FIGURE- Water vapor total integrated column computed from the MPCM (a) and from SPICAM measurements (b) for Martian Years 36 and 30 respectively. Panels c and d show the columns obtained from the MPCM from 0 to 120 km, and from 30 to 80 km respectively, both at the location of NOMAD observations during MYs 35 and 36. Panel e shows the columns computed with the water vapor profiles retrieved from NOMAD from 30 to 80 km during MYs 35 and 36. Panel f shows the relative difference between the columns from NOMAD and MPCM computed from 30 to 80 km. Blue colors indicate larger MPCM abundances than NOMAD.

656 a more efficient water vapor release and transport from the polar regions to lower latitudes.
 657 This same feature was also noticed by Rossi et al. (2022) (see their Figure 6), who reported
 658 similar discrepancies between ACS and a previous version of the MPCM during MYs 34
 659 and 35. In addition, although it is not discussed in their paper, their Figure 5 reveals
 660 also systematically higher temperatures at low altitudes during this same period, supporting
 661 the hypothesis of a more efficient water vapor release and transport. In contrast, during
 662 the perihelion, i.e. the second half of the MY, the differences between NOMAD and the
 663 MPCM are less dramatic in the northern hemisphere at low altitudes. In contrast, it is
 664 interesting to highlight the discrepancies observed during $L_S = 270^\circ - 330^\circ$ at ~ 60 km
 665 in the northern hemisphere. Particularly at the morning, this region shows some overestimation
 666 in the model perhaps due to water ice clouds formation in the atmosphere not well reproduced
 667 in the MPCM. This hypothesis is compatible with the results reported by Rossi et al. (2022),
 668 where they found that the water vapor condensation above 60 km is not correctly represented

669 in the model during this period of the year. As an alternative or as an additional reason
 670 of this this discrepancy, the excess of water in the northern hemisphere at 60 km and
 671 the overall deficit of water in the southern one could suggest an excessive northward transport
 672 from the southern hemisphere at middle altitudes. In addition, a deficient modeling of
 673 the strong water vapor injection to high altitudes at high southern latitudes could also
 674 be related with the observation that around 100 km in the northern hemisphere, the MPCM
 675 abundances are deficient compared to NOMAD. Since the model is not able to reproduce
 676 the high altitude southern water injection, it is not able either to reproduce the strong
 677 meridional transport at high altitudes leading to a water vapor deficit at 100 km in the
 678 northern hemisphere. With all these evidences over the table, the two most potential candidates
 679 to explain the observed discrepancies between model and observations during the perihelion
 680 season are the atmospheric temperatures and the water vapor supersaturation. Several
 681 variables are involved in these processes such as the so called particle contact parameters
 682 and ice cloud micro-physics. These two properties directly affect on the injection of water
 683 upwards and any excess/defect of the water condensation drives the altitude water vapor
 684 is able to reach.

685 For a better understanding of the NOMAD-MPCM discrepancies, one should not
 686 only look at the vertical distribution but also at the total water vapor column. We computed
 687 the water integrated columns from the MPCM profiles for the MYs 35 and 36 for both
 688 the whole latitudinal/seasonal grid (Figure 13-a) and at the location of NOMAD observations
 689 (Figure 13-c). We noticed that the total amount of water vapor from our simulations that
 690 is injected into the atmosphere is qualitative smaller than other previous simulations (Pottier
 691 et al. (2017), see their figure 9). This is particularly noticeable during the perihelion season
 692 in the southern polar region, where our simulated columns are about a factor 3 smaller.
 693 Although it is not possible to obtain full integrated columns from NOMAD SO observations
 694 due to the lack of measurements at the lowermost altitudes where the aerosol opacity
 695 is large, we compared simulated (Figure 13-d) and measured (Figure 13-e) water vapor
 696 columns by vertical integration in the altitude range between 30 and 80 km, region where
 697 full vertical profiles can be retrieved from NOMAD for most of the Martian year. This
 698 comparison shown in Figure 13-f suggests that, at least above 30 km, the largest discrepancies
 699 occur during the aphelion season. Particularly for the southern hemisphere at latitudes
 700 between 30° - 60° , the total amount of water observed with NOMAD is larger than the
 701 model's prediction. During this season in the northern hemisphere this statement is not
 702 clear, with regions of both excess and deficit of water. For the perihelion season the relative
 703 differences are smaller in the northern hemisphere and low southern latitudes with values
 704 about 10-20%. Nevertheless, although less dramatic than that observed during the aphelion
 705 season, again a deficit of water in our model's columns is observed mainly at the southern
 706 hemisphere supporting the aforementioned suggestion of a too small water injection in
 707 the southern hemisphere in our MPCM simulations.

708 **6.3 Water injection at high altitudes**

709 The strong injection of water vapor to very high altitudes observed with NOMAD
 710 (Brines et al., 2024; Villanueva et al., 2022) stands as a particular challenge for the MPCM.
 711 Brines et al. (2024), hereinafter referred to as BEA24, already highlighted that in MY34
 712 the mesospheric injection, or "plume", was also present but it was somehow weaker than
 713 in the following years and started later in the perihelion season. The comparison of the
 714 MY34 to MYs 35 and 36 performed by BEA24 showed that the discrepancy in water vapor
 715 was also present at tropospheric altitudes about 30° in solar longitude before the injection
 716 was observed, revealing lower abundances during MY 34. Considering this, we explored
 717 a couple of aspects in the MPCM to figure out why the model fails to reproduce such
 718 a plume and also why the water vapor is particularly deficient in MY 34. A first idea
 719 was the possibility that the sublimation of water ice from the southern hemisphere's polar
 720 and quasi-polar regions was much lower during MY 34, perhaps due to the GDS earlier
 721 that year. The rationale is that an increased deposition of dust at high latitudes may

Table 1: Summary of the six most relevant discrepancies between NOMAD and MPCM found in this work (left column) along with the most probable issues in the model causing them (right column)

Discrepancies	Potential cause
MPCM overestimates water vapor abundance during MY 34.	Dust vertical distribution not properly modeled. Too much heating by dust
Low altitude overestimation in the model during the aphelion in the northern hemisphere	Too much water ice sublimation from the north polar cap
MPCM underestimates abundances during LS=120 at both hemispheres	Global circulation too weak. Incorrect dust vertical distribution
Southern hemisphere's perihelion seasonal enhancement not properly reproduced in the MPCM	Global circulation not strong enough in the model
MPCM overestimates abundance at 60 km during LS=270-330 (northern hemisphere)	Too little water ice cloud formation in the model. Excess of northward transport at 50-80 km
MPCM underestimates abundance at high altitudes during LS=270-300 (both hemispheres)	Too little water ice sublimation from the southern polar region. Not enough vertical transport in the model.

722 reduce and delay the water ice sublimation. However estimations of the diffusion of water
723 through a dust layer indicate that such a layer needs to be as thick as several millimeters
724 thick to produce the desired effect. Such a thick layer has never been observed in polar
725 regions. For this reason we consider that the transport and deposition of dust in MY34
726 may not be directly affecting this water vapor injection. A second candidate, the transport
727 of water towards the southern polar regions (SPR) before the southern polar cap sublimation,
728 might not be relevant either, for the same reason. In addition, it seems that most of the
729 water vapor injected to the atmosphere from the SPR comes from fresh sublimation from
730 the polar caps, and not so much from meridional transport in the previous MY's water
731 cycle. Let us notice that the reason for the low water vapor abundance at high latitudes
732 following a GDS, which has also been observed by (Pankine et al., 2023), is still a mystery.
733 After disregarding these aspects, we consider as more likely that the plume is very sensitive
734 to the precise timing of the strongest water sublimation from the southern polar cap and/or
735 to the strength of the overturning circulation, and that this might not sufficiently strong
736 in the MPCM or it takes place at lower mesospheric altitudes.

737 6.4 Cluster analysis

738 Finally, being a purely statistical tool blind to physics, the cluster analysis performed
739 in this work revealed meaningful water vapor latitudinal and seasonal distributions, providing
740 a simplified water vapor climatology. The clustering successfully captured the water vapor
741 strong seasonal variability and resulted to be more sensitive to it above other variations
742 due to latitude or local time. Specific climatological events such as the peak of the MY
743 34 GDS or the water vapor pumping in the southern hemisphere during the perihelion
744 were assigned to distinct groups standing out as separate vertical profiles. Improving the
745 assignation method and focusing the analysis on specific periods could help to highlight

746 some of the interhemispheric and local time variations discussed here and in Paper I. The
 747 goal of this analysis was to provide a first and simplified view of the water vapor latitudinal/seasonal
 748 distribution, settling the framework for future studies on clustering of Martian water vapor
 749 vertical profiles, possibly focused on more specific times and locations. In addition, we
 750 also applied the clustering to the MPCM water vapor profiles. This revealed similar seasonal
 751 patterns as those observed with NOMAD, highlighting the high capability of the MPCM
 752 on reproducing the water cycle on Mars. However, above 60 km the vertical structure
 753 of the group profiles obtained from the MPCM differ from those obtained from NOMAD
 754 observations, showing a systematic wetter atmosphere in the model at high altitudes.

755 7 Conclusions

756 For this work, we analyzed NOMAD SO spectra from more than 7000 occultations
 757 collected over MYs 34 to 37, covering four different spectral regions and combining them
 758 in the vertical in order to avoid optically thick absorption lines. Our pre-processing pipeline
 759 significantly improved the correction of systematic errors in the NOMAD SO data, particularly
 760 for high-altitude measurements where accurate baseline characterization is crucial. This
 761 permitted the retrieval of extended water vapor vertical profiles from approximately 5
 762 km to 120 km altitude in a single consistent inversion. Our large data set allowed us to
 763 perform an exhaustive comparison not only with other teams and instruments but also
 764 with the MPCM. In addition, a novel post-processing strategy based on the statistical
 765 technique of cluster analysis was applied for the first time to Martian water vapor vertical
 766 profiles. Our main conclusions can be summarized as follows:

- 767 • The results presented in this work extend and complement previous recent studies
 768 on water vapor vertical profiles. Here we presented a comparison with other three
 769 TGO teams retrieving water vapor from observations by NOMAD and ACS and
 770 revealing overall good agreement between different teams and datasets.
- 771 • The comparison between NOMAD SO and the MPCM revealed the model's capability
 772 to properly simulate the most relevant seasonal patterns of the water vapor climatology
 773 during different MYs. However, some notorious discrepancies arise. The dust distribution
 774 during MY 34 is not properly reproduced in the MPCM, which leads to a systematic
 775 excess of the modeled water vapor abundances at both hemispheres during the whole
 776 second part of MY 34 (during and after the GDS). During the aphelion season,
 777 an excess of water vapor is observed in the model at low altitudes below 30 km
 778 while a lack of it is present above. This may be the result of an overestimation of
 779 the water vapor release from the North polar cap and/or a deficient vertical transport
 780 in the model during this season. During the perihelion of MYs 35 and 36, the vertical
 781 distribution of water vapor is underestimated in the model, possibly as a result
 782 of an underestimation of the dust vertical transport during this period. In addition,
 783 a deficit in the simulation of water ice formation above 60 km seem to be responsible
 784 of a wetter atmosphere at high altitudes during the second part of the year. These
 785 differences are intriguing and modeling efforts are very needed in order to find out
 786 a solution.
- 787 • We presented for the first time an application of cluster analysis techniques to NOMAD
 788 SO water vapor vertical profiles. We identified at least 6 distinct type of profiles
 789 representative of different atmospheric conditions and proving this technique to
 790 be useful for providing a simplified view of the water vapor climatology.
 791 Some efforts are ongoing in order to evaluate some of the discrepancies observed
 792 between NOMAD and ACS dataset and more comparison exercises will be needed
 793 to improve the agreement and reliability of the results. Moreover, from a modeling
 794 point of view, more observations and studies of the vertical distribution of water
 795 vapor are needed to not only extend the comparisons presented here, but also to
 796 improve the physics involved in the global climate models and to cross validate
 797 future model predictions and measurements.

Open Research Section

The NOMAD SO Level 1a calibrated data used in this work are available at the European Space Agency Planetary Science Archive (ESA, 2024). More information about the data on the PSA can be found in the NOMAD Experiment-to-Archive Interface Control Document (*EAI CD*, 2024). The results retrieved from the NOMAD SO measurements presented in this work are being archived and available at Brines, López-Valverde, Funke, González-Galindo, et al. (2025).

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